

Students' insufficient application abilities: An exploration of its causality in the Indian Context

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Abstract

This paper explored and examined the causes of the difficulties faced by students in applying what they learn in the classroom. It is often complained by recruiters that the students even at the end of their studies at undergraduate level are found, lacking the necessary abilities of applying their previously acquired knowledge for practical purposes when asked prospective workplace related questions during campus recruitment interviews. This phenomenon negatively impacts the country's socio-economic development, while appealing to the teaching fraternity to find a practicable solution to this problem. This is the research problem which is explored and examined, attempting to answer the question, "Why do students, in general, often fail to apply their knowledge as and when required"? It is hypothesized that the lack of tangible learning practices in the classroom is the central cause for the lack of application skills in students. Therefore, the objectives of this research were 1. To study the historical background of problem 2. To study and analyze the challenges that the students are confronting while learning and applying, 3. To study and understand the causes for the lack of application skills in students, 4. To analyze the relevant aspects of their academics at their respective learning places. This research was a qualitative dominant quantitative research. Hence, the research problem is qualitatively explored and these explored qualitative ideas in turn are examined with the help of the quantitative and qualitative data collected through the survey method.

Keywords: Tangible learning experience – rote-learning - Metacognition - Self-Regulation – Misconceptions – Learning strategies.

Introduction

It is often found by the teachers of English, in general, through their empirical classroom teaching experience that the students often face difficulties in using appropriate linguistic units in correct linguistic structures during their regular language lab practice sessions aside from their occasional participation in co-curricular activities held on campus. It is also the similar experience of the teachers of technology. In the domain of technology education, the students are, in general, confined only to the utility of a specific theorem/law in a specific situation only. They often run short of a skill set with which they can apply their acquired knowledge in different practical situations. This empirical experience of teachers during their classroom teaching sessions paved the basis for the necessity of exploring and examining the problem of the “insufficient application capabilities among the students and the exploration of the factors of its causality in the Indian context”.

The recruiters also often say that the students face difficulties in solving the problems during the technical rounds of campus placement interviews. The empirical observation of the researcher in regard to this general phenomenon paves the basis for the formation of an inference that the students must be facing the same issue in regard to their branch specific studies, too. However, the empirical experience and the consequent understanding will not be necessarily true. Such understanding needs to be ascertained through a scientific process which involves an objective study and analysis.

This research aims to answer the research question, why do students, in general, often fail to apply their knowledge as and when required? The other associated questions are as follows: Are they able to apply their knowledge and skill set when, at times, they need to resolve the issues in the classrooms. If they are not able to do this, what are the causes for this problem of learning? Or are there any problems with their cognitive learning abilities? How far are the current methods and approaches supportive for the educators to impart application skills among students? Do they habitually ignore the responsibility of acquiring the ability to apply their acquired knowledge in real time productive situations? ..., and so on.

Rationale for this Research

Learning is not for the mere retention of knowledge in passive memory nor just for securing a better grade during examinations. In fact, the process of learning constitutes a major aim, i.e., learning is for application in practical situations. The students at undergraduate level, in general, are expected to join social production soon after they complete their formal education. However, the students, according to previous surveys, are unable to apply what they learn at the academic institutions. Indian job market, in fact, struggling to get employable educated youth. The research report of National Skill Development Corporation (NSDC) discloses that “the demand for skilled labor in India reached approximately 103 million workers in 2022. However, the supply fell short by 29 million workers” (How India Can Bridge ...2024). This phenomenon casts a challenge to the efforts in the process of socio-economic development of the society. Because of the persistence of this problem among students, the higher salary package campus recruitments are mostly confined only to top ranked educational institutions such as IITs, IIMs, NITs, Central Universities. Students are being recruited sporadically even from the affiliated colleges, but the number of students with employability is lower than the required. It happens so due to their embracing of unproductive learning strategies, one of which is a rote memorization through which the knowledge is retained in their passive memory.

The tendency of “learning and forgetting” is a weakness among students. This weakness causes their being in the back waters in the international job market. Even if some students are recruited to work at a company, they are unable to take up the workplace responsibilities soon after they join the work. On some other occasions, they are not even acquainted with the workplace jargon as per some reports. Even the students who are recruited by the corporate software companies, which conduct placement drives at the ranked universities, institutes and autonomous and affiliated colleges essentially undergo training programs. To exemplify the scenario, Tata Consultancy Company conducts a three-month training program for its fresher engineering graduates (What are the daily...2022), while this duration of the training at Infosys is from three to six months (Infosys Training for ... 2020). It is only at Microsoft that the training period is conducted only for four weeks (Students and Graduates), whereas the training period at Cognizant company lasts up to six months (Cognizant Internship...2022). The companies like Cognizant recruit students at the ranked universities. However, the recruits are considered as Interns; they are

to undergo rigorous training in the domains such as job specific “hands-on experience and behavioral learning” with an objective of becoming “technologically competent” (ibid). While the students who are from research backed institutes and universities do require a pre-service training program or an internship, can the students from other institutes (where the research goes on at a slower pace) settle comfortably in their prospective workplaces without rigorous pre-service training programmes? Hence, the “learn and forget” academically impaired situation needs to be replaced with the “learn and apply” one, which is a productive teaching-learning academic environment.

Aside from the job-interview-perspective, this application deficiency among students compels one to view the problem from a far broader perspective. Because, either a student or an employee or anyone else is basically a human being whose relations are tangled with several social units such as economy, culture, family, religion, politics and so on. They will have to utilize their knowledge in various ways and forms (being part of various social units) when they run across specific difficult situations in their social lives. Moreover, the humans’ social activity is not just confined only to the workplaces; they are to deal with several other diversified issues in their familial and socio-cultural living spheres. The problems they deal within these spheres are different from one another, but they too are as important as the ones they deal with in their respective workplaces. So, the acquisition of problem-solving through the efficient use of an application related skill set is required for any country to achieve a progressive and prosperous socio-economic development. However, the problem solving processes regarding these issues require more abilities of application than their memorized pre-acquired knowledge which is passively stored in the repositories of their minds. Because the students have only their respective domain specific knowledge acquired in their classrooms and labs of their academic institutions, whereas the problems they run across in their prospective workplaces and in their daily social lives are not as exactly as they anticipate the ones they face while they are at academic institutions. So, viewing a problem from a broader perspective is a prerequisite for one to understand the problem and apply a suitable strategy as a means for problem solving in real life situations.

The design thinking pedagogues also assert this educational need through their curricula of Design Thinking for Innovation. Real life situations are different from one another in workplaces besides socio-economic, cultural and familial spheres. The students are to be necessarily equipped

with the capability of resolving these diversified problems they run across in the various spheres of their social lives. Hence, the research into the investigation of the causality of the phenomena of the student's insufficient application abilities at their learning places is significant and relevant.

More importantly, a student-turned-employee is expected to contribute to the process of sustainable growth and development of the organization where they are employed and thereby making their contribution to the country's socio-economic development process in which they themselves are an integral part. When a problem which has been causing harm to the interests of the whole society and thereby standing as a formidable hurdle in the way of the country's progress, that problem needs to be addressed. Hence, the problem of the students' insufficient application abilities and finding the factors that cause the persistence of this problem in the arena of education is worth researching and an immediate necessity for the progressive, sustainable socio-economic development of the country.

Though India has had a rich past in regard to the education system with a methodological approach which consisted of lecture and discussions in the ancient and early medieval ages, the rich past seemed to have lost its legacy in the present era. The lack of application skills among students is a major concern. In an attempt to overcome this problem, the University Grants Commission (UGC) introduced Learning Outcomes-Based Curriculum Framework in 2018. The expert talks on this issue are taking place at regular intervals in the universities for every now and then. However, if the aspects like, the necessity of the provision of required infrastructure on campus and the creation of feasible teaching-learning schedule for imparting the course contents are not taken into serious consideration, the well-intentioned objective of the UGC, "Outcome-Based Education" remains an unsuccessful attempt in imparting application skills to the students at undergraduate level. These two aspects are to be explored and examined through the real-time experiments in various different learning places. However, these aspects are left unexplored for future researchers to choose as their research problem. So, the current research is limited to the exploration and examination of the factors that cause the students' insufficient application skills and the causes for this phenomenon in this era in which the methodological approach at an educational institute is not in favor of Application of the memorized information.

Literature Review

Though the problem of application of the acquired knowledge in real life situations is significant and ever relevant, much research has not been done. However, a few researchers published research articles from different perspectives. David McNamara worked on the problems and possibilities of teachers in the context of student teachers' knowledge issues and reforms in his *Subject Knowledge and its Application: problems and possibilities for teacher educators* in 1991. This research paper centered on the tendency of the policy makers in Britain and the USA that "are promoting student teachers' knowledge of subjects and their application of subject knowledge in the classroom as a key element in the reform of teacher training" (David 1991).

W.H. Taylor worked on the status of the yesteryear education system in India and its aspects in his research paper, *Preparing Teachers for the Universalizing of Education in India* in the 1990s. The focus of this research article was on how the Indian education system was not able to reach the under-privileged sections in India while this education system is facilitating only the privileged sections' children to be educated.

S.J. Van Zolingen's work encased the Application problem as one of its constituents. He studied the problem of Knowledge management among various companies and how various phases of the knowledge management process are distinguished from one another. According to this researcher, "the five phases of the knowledge management process" are: "Acquiring knowledge, codifying knowledge, disseminating knowledge, developing knowledge and applying knowledge" (S.J. Van 2002). In his case study titled, *Problems in Knowledge Management: A Case Study of a Knowledge-Intensive Company* revealed that the problem of Knowledge management mostly "occurred in the first three phases" (ibid). However, the knowledge application problem was not specifically researched in this paper also.

Other than the research endeavors whose details mentioned above, no substantial research has been conducted in this arena. Hence, this phenomenon has formed a gap for the chosen research problem which is necessary for further growth and development of students.

Research Question

Hence, the central research question, "Why do students, in general, often fail to apply their knowledge as and when required"?

Hypothesis

It is hypothesized that the lack of tangible learning practices in the classroom is the central cause for the lack of application skills in students.

The interrogation of the research problem is carried out in light of the words of Martin King that “tangible learning engages the whole person, not just the intellectual mind, it emphasizes practical, active and activity learning and the value of doing and getting stuff done in the real world”. (Martin King 2017).

Research Objectives

Therefore, the objectives of this research are 1. To study the historical background of problem 2. To study and analyze the challenges that the students are confronting while learning and applying, 3. To study and understand the causes for the lack of application skills in students, 4. To analyze the relevant aspects of their academics at their respective learning places.

The Scope of the Research

The objectives specified above determine the scope of the research. The research is confined to the limits of investigating the problem for knowing the factors for its causality. It is assumed that once the factors that have caused the problem to persist even in the age of the advanced science and technology are known, the problem can easily be dealt with by the teachers and educationists. The ways of dealing with a problem are nothing but the rational attempts of resolving the same.

Limitations

This research is confined only to the unraveling of the factors of causality of students’ inability in applying what they learn in their classrooms. So, the focus of the research is majorly on the causes rather than the solutions suggested if any. Because, the proposed solutions, if any, at the end of this pursuit are necessarily to be deductively proved to be productive and practicable. This forms the scope for future research.

The Method of Research

This research is carried out, using an inductive approach. So, the data collection is done in the select colleges in the select place or places. In inductive research, the data collection is done in a limited research place or places. Later, the findings' analysis is generalized. This generalization is to be deductively proved by later researchers in future.

However, methodologically, this research is a qualitative dominant quantitative research. So, the problem is qualitatively explored and the qualitative discourse in turn is quantitatively examined with the support of the quantitative and qualitative data collected through the survey method. This is a triangulation method which comprises both the qualitative and quantitative methods and this method is necessary for the research to be carried out with the chosen research problem. The research problem needs to be thoroughly studied qualitatively and the findings of this study need to be verified through the process of the quantification of the collected data. The qualitative study is carried out by the study of the required data available in libraries –both physical and online libraries-- and the data collected subjectively from various participants. This subjective data needs to be verified by objectively quantifiable data collected from the same. So, the data collection involves referencing various texts such as research articles, books, website studies etc., in various domains of knowledge aside from collecting the data through questionnaires afresh from the participants. So, the tools for data collection include both the quantitative and qualitative questionnaires. The qualitative questionnaires consist of subjective questions, trying to ascertain some selected quantitative questions' responses, while the quantitative ones consist of a 7-point Likert scale questionnaires aside from "Yes/No" answer questionnaires. This research is predominantly qualitative with the rational support of the quantifiable data. The investigation of the chosen problem involves more of the collection of concrete facts and the interrogation of the same. So, the researcher's method of inquiry involves the following:

1. The study of the history of the problem, which has long been persisting in human society.
2. Understanding the problem from various required perspectives.
3. The collection of quantifiable data through survey, qualitatively and quantitatively.
4. Analyze and evaluate the data within the framework of the qualitative dominant quantitative method. This process involves the dialectical application of the researcher's

knowledge related to the education sphere gained previously while the research is being carried out. However, the researcher is aware of the potential errors that would often take place due to the unconscious subjectivity. Hence, the analysis of the collected data is always to be done, being aware of this problem of the unconscious subjective understanding and interpretation which usually occurs due to the erroneous mental process of “the slip of mind” as Sigmund Freud felt in another context of his clinical psychiatry.

5. The process of the analysis and evaluation is followed by the proposition. The researcher has made a hypothesis in the beginning of the discourse of this paper. It is expected that the stated hypothesis could be proved true. However, it is still remained unknown whether the hypothesis would be proved true or the findings would guide the researcher to make a proposition which may be opposite to the mentioned hypothesis at the end of this research endeavors.

6. As the data collection centers are limited in number, located in one single state, i.e., Andhra Pradesh, India, the approach of this research is inductive and so these findings are to be verified deductively by future researchers.

7. The research now begins with the qualitative study of the history of the problem.

Historical Background of the Problem of Application in Indian Context

It is commonly agreed that the objective of a teaching faculty is not limited to “read and remember”, but to the imparting of inclusive education to the students with an objective of “learn and apply”. In fact, the practice of “read, recite, remember and reproduce” had not been in vogue even in the era of ancient Gurukuls [educational institutions] that functioned several ages ago. According to the study of Future Learn, “Gurukul was India’s first education system” and “this was a residential schooling system” which had facilitated to grow and strengthen a bond of love and trust between “the Sishya [student] and the Guru [teacher]” (Explore: The education system in India. 2023). This study further reveals that these Gurukuls had an objective of the attainment of “holistic development” of pupils. This education system aimed to safeguard the “mental, cognitive, physical and spiritual wellness” of the students. More importantly, as per the data found in this website article, the ancient Gurukul education system upheld the process of developing “student’s human values such as self-reliance, empathy, creativity, plus strong moral and ethical behaviors” (ibid). It was also opined in the same study that these acquired values would help

students apply what they learnt at the Gurukul “could later be practically implemented to find solutions to [their] real-life problems” (ibid). How the-then Gurukuls functioned was remembered only to remind one the necessity of understanding today’s education system in light of the phenomenon of the values-based education system prevailed ages ago with an objective “learn and apply”.

The mode of teaching-learning process in ancient and medieval periods were relatively progressive though their focus was not on the application in the market economy. Several historical facts testify to this. The three major universities Takshashila, Nalanda and Vikramashila in ancient and medieval periods stood as exemplar in the arena of education with progressive student centric teaching-learning methodologies. Takshashila which was established between 5th and 6th centuries BCE and remained in existence till the 5th century AD until the invasions of Hun Kings was the center for learning. Nalanda established in 427 CE continued to be in existence till 1197 CE was visited by Chinese traveler Xuan Zang [627 – 643 AD] also known as Hiuen Tsang. According to Jayanthi Chattopadhyay, “Hiuen Tsang visited Nalanda Mahavihara (= Monastic University) in 637 AD” and studied there at Shilabhadra. Hiuen Tsang here stayed for five years, being both as a student and teacher and “recorded over a hundred lectures” taught by teachers at this university with the “help of I-Quing, a fellow Buddhist Monk and translator” and observed that the mode of teaching here consisted of “debates and discussions” (Nalanda University and role of community). Holding debates and discussions on the premises of educational institutions under the-then absolute monarchies is relatively progressive, reminding one the necessity of the adoption of these progressive methods of teaching by today’s educational institutes.

Aside from this progressive feature, there used to be a student centric approach at these educational institutes where students had plenty of opportunities to acquire application skills while imparting various courses. Several different courses that were offered at these universities, keeping discussions and debates as tools of the student-centric approach of teaching. The courses offered, here, to the students were not confined to the realm of spiritual education whereas they constitute the courses such as “the Scriptures of Eighteen Schools (Nikayas) of Buddhism, Brahmanical Shastras, Different Systems of Indian Philosophy, Grammar, Philology, Medical Science, Astrology, Astronomy were most efficiently taught” as being opined by Jayanthi Chattopadhyay” (Chattopadhyay. 2003). All these courses were necessary for one in one’s social life. Furthermore,

the courses were taught by embracing progressive teaching methods. The study of Sirish Kumar. S and Rudrawar et al mention in their research work “Education System in India” that the students were to “memorize all the things” in the absence of books, but “they used to deep dive into the concepts taught by their teachers and explore new methods to learn it”. This study asserts the freedom of students to raise questions, debating and discussing among one another in those days. The teachers here “used the storytelling methods to teach the students” and “the education of that time mainly focused on practical knowledge of the topics taught in the class” (Sirish Kumar. S). These facts testify that there used to be a progressive education system in the ancient Indian universities which included not only remember and recitation but also debates and discussions which are essential characteristics of a student-centric educational approach through which the students can gain application skills. The level of attainment of “Apply” by students becomes possible only when the educators encourage debates and discussions among students and between the students and teachers.

In the later ages, predominantly the religious shrines and buildings housed the educational institutions. While the Temple yards housed the schools for the students of Hindus, Madrasas “emerged during the 10th century as independent [educational] institutions” (Madrasas as Universal Centers of Education and Culture) imparted education to Muslim pupils. The methods of teaching – learning at these institutes were distinct. The study of the Test Book website reveals that the students at Madrasas “learn through memorization and repetition”, while the students at Gurukuls “learn through oral recitation and discussions” (Education in medieval India... 2023). Though it is widely believed that the medieval period in Indian history was excessively religious, the ideas of Abul Faz’l are worth considering.

Abul Faz’l’s Proposal & Application Skills

Though the-then times were religion-ridden ones, the progressive attempts to reform the education sphere were made by some scholars like Abul Faz’l at King Akbar’s court. The report on education reforms by Abul Faz’l reveals King Akbar’s reformative world outlook. The “scholarly advisor” of King Akbar advised the then monarchical government in his report that the students are not to be over-burdened with the reading of too many texts and memorizing the same, whereas they are to be imparted cognitive skills in identifying the letters, words and their meanings in sentences. Once acquired the skill in this regard, Abul Faz’l opined that the boys [students] would be able to

“read books on morals (akhlak)”, and understand “arithmetic (hisab), the accountancy (siyaq), agriculture (falihat), mensuration (masahat), geometry (handasah), astronomy (nujum), physiognomy (ramal), household matters (tadbor - I - manzil), the rules of the government (siasat – I – madan), medicine (tibb), logic (mantic), physical sciences (ilm – I – tabi i), sciences, spiritual sciences (ilm – I – ilahi), as well as history (tarokh)” and so on. In addition to this, Abul Faz’l opines that the Sanskrit-learners are to learn “byakaran (grammar), Bedanta (Vedanta), and Patanjali (Yoga)” (Rezavi. 2007). Finally, Faz’l asserts that all the points mentioned above are to be mandatorily implemented and therefore, “no one should be allowed to neglect those things which the present time requires ...” (Rezavi. 2007). This way of systematic study, according to him, would help the students acquire knowledge in the above domains. Abul Faz’l’s vision is still worth considering in teaching – learning processes. Abul Faz’l’s model was nearer to the learning objective of ‘application’ which is the third indicator of Blooms Taxonomy. Because, his advocacy of better cognitive skills in identifying the meaning and the structures of letters, words, and sentences would help students enhance their brainstorming intrapersonal skills which are necessary for one to apply what they learn.

Education System under the East India Company Regime

The so-called modern education began during the regime of the British East India Company which had hardly identified the necessity of applying knowledge that is learnt by students. When the company required clerical assistance and when there was a huge scarcity of its own men, it envisioned to spread the western English education in India. In compliance with its urgent economic needs, it set up schools and colleges in some parts of India. The study of Jagranjosh website reveals several facts in regard to the education system in India since the times of British East India Company. According to this study, “two missionary activists Charles Grant and William Wilberforce” appealed to the then British Government to begin English education in India with a view “to teaching western literature and preaching Christianity” (Development of education ...). The 1813 Act came into force and allocated “one lakh” (ibid) for the establishment of schools in India. It is because of “the efforts of R.R.M. Roy [Raja Ram Mohan Roy], the Calcutta college [today’s Presidency University]” (ibid) came into existence in then Bengal in 1817. However, there was an uproar in regard to the medium of teaching. While some Indian scholars objected to the induction of English as a medium, some other scholars invited the English language as a

medium of instruction. This scholarly strife caused the delay in allocating funds for the spread of western education in India.

The General Committee of Public Instruction was constituted in 1823. This riddle however was resolved by the controversial Macaulay educational policy 1835 in regard to the induction of English medium education in the country. It can be deduced from the phenomenon of the establishment of “the Calcutta College” that there was a specific aim of bringing in socio-cultural awakening among the Indian middle class. In the last analysis, the founders of this college had a vision in mind that the students educated at this college would apply their learning the contemporary social phenomena from a modern scientific perspective. So, the establishment of “Calcutta College” marked a new epoch in the sphere of Indian education.

The colonial rulers employed several commissions to modernize the education system in India. They are, however, confined only to a limited role of making Indians acquainted with English literacy and modern machine operations. Some of the facts in this regard are as follows: In accordance with the guidelines of Macaulay, the “Persian” language “was abolished” and it was replaced with “the English language” (ibid). The Macaulay committee was succeeded by the guidelines of Wood’s Dispatch 1854, which recommended “vernacular language” as the medium of teaching at “Primary level” and “Vernacular – Anglican at high school level” and the English language medium at higher level education (ibid). The Hunter Commission formed during 1882-83 to “evaluate” the outcomes of “Wood’s Dispatch 1854 under WW Hunter in 1882” (ibid). This commission asserted the necessity of enhancement of “state’s role in the extension and improvement of primary education and secondary education”, recommending “two division secondary education – Literary up to university; Vocational for commercial career” (ibid). The Saddler Commission was appointed in 1917 to “inquire about the conditions and prospects of Calcutta university” (manishsiq. 2023). Ever from the Act of 1813 to Saddler Commission in 1917, the colonial rulers emphasized what was to be taught and in which medium was it to be done. However, the imparting of ethical application of sciences and philosophy was not an educational objective in the agenda of the colonial rulers. This problem of application by the students still remained unaddressed even in the two volumes of Bombay Plan during the years 1944 and 1945.

Contribution of Indian Freedom Fighters to Education Sphere

Indian freedom fighters established the institutions to spread modern education among the Indian youth with a view to arousing national spirit in Indian youth. They expected that the educated youth in their modern educational institutions would apply what they learn in attaining modernity and autonomy.

During the regime of the British, several Indian freedom fighters, social reformers, industrialists, scientists and so on endeavored to spread modern education in the country. Syed Ahmad Khan established Aligarh Muslim University in 1875 (Founders of Indian Universities) with a view to imparting a modern world outlook among the Muslims. Vishnushastri Chiplunkar and Lokmanya Bal Gangadhar Tilak established The Deccan Education Society on the 24th October 1884. Within a few months thereafter they along with Vaman Sivaram Apte, Gopal Ganesh Agarkar and Mahadeo Ballal Namjoshi “started Fergusson College, Pune on the 2nd January 1885” (Our Founders...) to modernize the Indians while striving to retain the progressive traditional values. Madan Mohan Malaviya in 1916 established Benaras Hindu University, Rabindranath Tagore established Santiniketan [Viswa Bharti University] in 1921. Osmania university was established in 1918 by Mir Osman Ali Khan Akbar Hydari. Jamshedji Tata established Indian Institute of Science in 1909, while Homi J Baba and J.R.D. Tata together established Tata Institute of Fundamental Research in 1945 (Founders of Indian Universities). These endeavors were partially borne fruit in making the middle class attain national consciousness. Those educated at these institutions seemed to have applied what they learnt in language, philosophy and modern sciences by actively taking part in freedom struggles either as moderates or extremists.

The Education System after Independence - The UGC

After the independence in 1947, The University Grants Commission was formed on the 28th December 1953 and it became a statutory body in November 1956 through the enactment of a bill in Indian Parliament. The study of Wikipedia website mentions that as of 14 November 2023, a total of 1114 universities including 56 Central universities, 479 state universities, 124 Deemed universities, 455 private universities were established (List of universities in India). Other than these, there are 95 autonomous educational institutions (List of autonomous higher education ...) such as IITs, IIMs, NITs, IIITs, AIIMS and so on were granted authority by the Indian Parliament

to award degrees. However, Indian education institutes are yet to attain the world's best rankings which are determined based on “two major factors viz., “Global opportunity index and Quality index” according to the study of Yashita Sinha (Best Education System 2024). The six levels of Blooms Taxonomy, which includes ‘Application’ with an indicating level 3, are employed in almost every educational institution in India while imparting and assessing the learning standards of students.

The decision of the University Grants Commission to bring in reforms in the evaluation of students performance at educational institutions reasserts the necessity of imparting application skills to the students. In its note of instructions to all the education bodies in the country mentioned that “Current examination system tests memory learning skills” (Evaluation Reforms ...). Further it stated that “Demands from profession require students not just to possess information but an individual application to every situation either routine or complex. This necessitates pressure on students to perform to the best of their capabilities. Memory learning may be required but not adequate to perform in the challenging environment that currently prevails. There is a need to assess application skills or skills of higher ability like analysis, creation, evaluation etc...” (ibid). This is a progressive understanding by the UGC that the students lack application ability due to memory testing evaluation patterns. This academic loophole needs to be covered up with rational planning and dialectical teaching practices.

Poor Application Skills: The Necessity of Imparting Cognitive Skills to Students

Learning process majorly includes cognition of material things and abstract concepts. Cognition happens in several ways through several sources. The practical knowledge displayed by several older generation persons testify this truth. They, without having regular schooling, display wisdom, resolving the issues in their daily social lives. Dr APJ Abdul Kalam re-asserts this truth in his Ignited Minds, saying that the knowledge can be acquired “through various other sources like libraries, researches, seminars, [and] drawings” (The Knowledge Society ...2016). However, the systematic learning at an educational institute or a university is unique and its productivity is more. When students possess the better cognitive abilities, they can step ahead to apply what they have learnt.

It is necessary for the educators to eliminate all the distractors that stand as obstacles in the process of cognition among students. According to Stephen Chew, the professor of psychology at Samford University, there are nine challenges “that teachers and students must overcome... These challenges include, student mental mindset, metacognition and self-regulation, student fear and mistrust, lack of prior knowledge, misconceptions, ineffective learning strategies, transfer of learning, constraints of selective attention, and constraints of mental effort and working memory (Stephen Chew. 2023). All these cognitive aspects cast a challenge to the students in applying what they learn in the classroom. Hence, it is necessary to discourse the major problems that stand as obstacles in the teaching-learning process in a nut shell. This is done as part of the qualitative exploration of the answers for the chosen research questions in accordance with the research objectives set.

Next, the perspective and analysis of Stephen Chew, the professor of psychology at Samford University, Alabama, the USA is accessible and therefore their views are worth discoursing. So, the “nine challenges” (Cognitive Challenges... 2022) mentioned by professor Stephen Chew in collaboration with William Cerbin, the professor emeritus of psychology and founding director of the Center for Advancing Teaching and Learning at the University of Wisconsin-La Crosse are taken into consideration for brief study and analysis over which the research progresses towards the exploration of the research question, “why do students, in general, often fail to apply their knowledge in their real life productive situations?”.

The nine challenges that teachers and students are to overcome are as follows:

Student mental mindset, Metacognition and Self-Regulation, Student Fear and Mistrust, Lack of Prior Knowledge, Misconceptions, Ineffective Learning Strategies, Transfer of Learning, Constraints of Selective Attention, Constraints of Mental Effort and Working Memory. The data were collected from the Technology and the Pharmacy students at undergraduate level in two phases. During the first phase of data collection, one hundred and seventy students participated and forty five questions to be answered were given to them. As the students chose to give ideal answers rather than genuinely evaluating and expressing their respective learning phenomena. Hence, this situation of dilemma compelled the researcher to choose the conducting of the second phase of the survey. During the second phase of the data collection, two hundred and eighty three students took part in the survey. This time twenty four questions were given to them to respond.

The required data have been collected from the participants through the Google forms which are the qualitative dominant quantitative questionnaires to understand and analyze their abilities and learning habits at their respective learning places.

Student Mental Mindset: Application Skills

The mind sets of students determine the success of teaching – learning process at educational institutes. Majorly, there are two types of mind sets; they are fixed mind set and growth mind set. While the fixed mindset is unproductive and thereby a hamper to the further growth of the persons, the growth mindset is productive and it paves a way for the extensive growth and development of the individuals. So, it is necessary for teachers to nurture the students with a growth mindset.

While the fixed mindset makes students become complacent and thereby stoic in regard to their limited knowledge and skill set, the growth mindset propels them to grow and expand their skill set. Carol Dweck (2000) writes that “those with a fixed mindset view intelligence as innate and fixed from birth” but “those with a growth mindset believe intelligence is flexible; we can learn and improve through perseverance” (Dweck’s Theory of Mindset). In another context, Dweck (2006) reveals that the “learning behaviours are influenced when students understand their mindsets” (cited from Kari Mueller’s How Mindsets Impact Learning. 2019). Discouraging the factors that could influence the learning process of students at academic institutions, Kari Mueller, a researcher emphasizes the necessity of the transformation of “fixed mindset” to “growth mindset” (ibid. p4) which helps them know their potential to expand their academic horizons to achieve greater knowledge and skill set. In this regard, one is reminded of the words of Dweck (2006) that “as educators, it is critical to help students understand that their brains are malleable and can be stretched” (ibid. p.4), while Blackwell et al. (2007) asserted that the “mindset can be changed” and a change in mindset led to a change in grades of class 7 students (Dweck’s Theory of Mindset). So, the students who are with a fixed mind set are to be sensitized about its unproductive consequences.

The dormant presence of the elements of the fixed mindset in the subconscious minds of students stands as an obstacle in their way of the cognition of the inputs given by their teachers and the above facts reasserts that the students with fixed mindsets are to be enlightened on the necessity of the transformation of their fixed mindsets to the growth mindsets. Hence, it is reiterated from the exploration whose aspects mentioned above that the Lack of growth mindset

among students is one of the causes for their failure of timely application of the acquired knowledge. Also it is growth mindset which is as a solution that can liberate students from the regressive complacency and academic inertia that are the adverse consequences of the fixed mindset. The growth mindset needs to be nurtured among students for their better cognitive abilities.

The researcher's survey findings reveal that the students, in general, are with a growth mind set. When asked whether they believe that their knowledge and skill set are not fixed but could grow and change, 49.4% agreed, while 29.4% strongly agreed and 14.7% partly agreed. Nearly, 79% (excluding the 14.7% partly agreed students) of students are confident that they can better their skill set. This indicates the possession of a growth mind set by students in general.

When asked to probe deeply whether they are in the belief that their learning capabilities are too limited that they cannot expand their knowledge base as good as one of their favorite teacher's or role-model's, 38.2% of students agreed. While 20.6% of students partly agreed, 5.3 % strongly agreed.

In the last analysis, it can be deduced that about 64% of students have a poor self-esteem with a fixed mindset. The two questions aimed to get an answer on their mind set were differently answered. At first, they expressed their confidence that their skill set would grow. Later, they, however, were not able to retain in themselves their self-esteem when they were asked specifically whether their skill set would ever be improved to match with that of their role models. So, the answer to the later question confirms that the students in general lack a growth mind set. The students fail to acquire a growth mindset due to the prevalence of the lack of tangible teaching-learning environment at the educational institute. The lack of a growth mind set in students in turn implies the lack of application abilities of students in their academic and real life situations.

Metacognition and Self-Regulation

From the young children to the young students need to have cognitive skills. It helps them identify the things around them besides understanding the internal relationship among them. The undergraduates, however, do require metacognition skills aside from self-regulated study skills. While cognitive skill is the ability of students' thinking and understanding in regard to their surroundings, metacognition is their ability to have "awareness and control of [their] thinking" (Cross and Paris, 1988, cited from Julie Dangremond et al., "Knowledge of Learning ..."). Brown opines, that the process of "metacognition framework consists of two parts: metacognitive knowledge and metacognitive regulation" (Brown, 1978 cited from Julie Dangremond et al., "Knowledge of Learning ..."). While metacognitive knowledge is "what learners know about their own thinking, including what they know about approaches for learning" (ibid), metacognitive regulation is student's "planning, monitoring and evaluating which are also important parts of self-

regulated learning” (Zimmerman, 1986, cited from Julie Dangremond et al., “Knowledge of Learning ...”). Julie Dangremond et al., opine that the “students with strong metacognitive regulation skills know how to select and implement learning strategies as part of their study plans [and] they can evaluate the effectiveness of their individual strategies as well as their overall [study] plans” (Julie Dangremond Stanton, Kathryn Morris Dye, Me’Shae Johnson. 2019). Hence, the students at undergraduate level need to know the assessment of their learning strategies while distinguishing between the teaching strategies of different teachers.

In order to further the interrogation in this regard, the researcher collected the data, asking students whether they have their own learning strategies and have capability to judge the effectiveness of the teaching-learning process, surprisingly a substantial proportion of the participants in the survey revealed that they have had their own learning strategies besides having the required capabilities to judge the effectiveness of teaching-learning process they experience in their respective classrooms. The majority of the students, however, admitted that they usually learn the contents by heart when asked during the second phase of the survey. Learning the content by heart is not a strategy. In fact, those with this regressive practice of learning contents by heart cannot have their own productive learning strategies. This phenomenon is the result of the lack of tangible teaching-learning environment in the classroom. The tangible learning practice which is an active learning practice includes promoting student autonomy also in the teaching-learning process. So, in the absence of the tangible teaching-learning environment in the classroom, the students are usually prone to embrace unproductive learning strategies like learning things by heart. This tendency of learning contents by heart stands as an obstacle in their way of attaining application capabilities.

Student Fear and Mistrust

The lack of tangible teaching-learning environment in the classroom causes mistrust of students in their faculty. Students are often found inactive in the classroom if they lack trust in their faculty and thereby they fear to execute their academic assignments even in the physical presence of their teachers. According to Stephen L Chew, the student will have trust in the teacher when the latter is “committed to student success” (Student fear ...). Stephen L Chew further says that “negative emotional reactions such as fear, or lack of trust in the teacher, can undermine motivation and

interfere with learning” (ibid). This aspect of mistrust in the teachers and fear of them stand as an obstacle in their way of the acquisition of application skills.

When asked whether they make a mistake even after the teacher explained correctly, 34.1% of students agreed that they commit an error. 23.5% partly agreed while 7.6% strongly agreed that they commit mistakes even after the teacher’s correct explanation. Altogether, 65% of students admitted that they commit mistakes even after they are imparted.

This shows their mistrust in their faculty from whom they learn things. In light of Stephen L Chew’s words, “one can understand that the students’ lack of trust in the teacher demotivates them, adversely interfering with their learning”. It is true that the negative emotional reactions such as fear and mistrust in teachers cause the occurrence of demotivation among students. A demotivated student naturally cannot cognise the learning materials and thereby he or she cannot apply what they have learnt in the classroom. Especially, the new language learning involves active application of the language rules. However, the demotivation among those students adversely impacts their language acquisition and application abilities. Xiaobin and Jirapa Abhakorn write that “demotivation is one of the important factors causing students’ failure in learning a language” (Xiaobin 2022). This demotivation also causes the formation of the mistrust of students in their teaching faculty. Eventually, this phenomenon will hamper the process of cognition and the application ability of students.

Lack of Prior Knowledge and Misconceptions

Students often fail to understand the contents and apply their acquired knowledge due to the formation of misconceptions in their minds. It happens and recurs due to the students’ exposure to

faulty conceptual knowledge. While the students acquire this faulty conceptual knowledge due to their exposure to faulty knowledge sources, sometimes, due to their own subjective understanding, they deliberately choose to embrace the faulty information. Since the 1980s, this has been a seriously recurring problem in the formal educational sphere. Clement's research in 1982 found that "88% of engineering and science students had misconceptions about the motion of objects at the start of their introduction to mechanics course" (Misconceptions...). These were called "Pre-course misconceptions by Clement. The students were also found "performing well", making almost no "errors on these types of problems" (ibid) during the conduct of the course work. However, the students committed the same mistake after completion of their course. Clement's experiment found that "75% of students who had passed in their post course tests made the same types of errors as pre-course students, reverting back to their earlier misconceptions" (Misconceptions...). This experiment shows an application gap in the learning process of students. Students, according to the aspects mentioned above, are unable to apply their gained knowledge in the academic situations.

The possession of the authentic prior knowledge is a pre-requisite for the cognition of the imparted knowledge in the right way. According to Stephen Chew and Cerbin, students confront the learning problems due to lack of prior knowledge of topics. Their study reveals that "the learning is likely to be fragmented and incomplete, when students lack relevant background knowledge" (Prior Knowledge). It is true that the students' lack of prior knowledge about various denotative and connotative meanings of words stands as an impediment in their way of acquiring application skills. Hence, the students are to be trained, acquainting themselves with the background knowledge of the topics before they are exposed to the learning contents. However, the answer of the majority of students in this regard differs with Stephen L. Chew and Cerbin's research findings.

When asked whether they can understand the lesson even without prior background knowledge, 35.3% of students agreed, while 23.5% partly agreed and 5.9% strongly agreed. In fact, without necessary prior background knowledge one cannot fully comprehend the new text. The students, however, mentioned that they were able to comprehend the new information even without necessary prior background knowledge. In fact, they think that they could understand the content without the prior background knowledge, whereas they are unaware of the gaps in their comprehension while listening to the lectures and reading the books. Susan et al mention that "...to comprehend a text, readers will need a threshold of knowledge about the topic. ... Without such knowledge, it becomes difficult to construct a meaningful mental model of what the text is about" (Susan). Therefore, even though the students (nearly 65%) answered that they were able to comprehend the lesson even without background knowledge, they face several difficulties in understanding the contents. The previous research surveys and the researcher's experiential knowledge assert that the students, without having understood the significance of prior background knowledge and without knowing how to assess their listening comprehension abilities expressed their opinion.

Collaborative learning is an essential aspect of tangible teaching-learning process in the classroom. The collaborative learning facilitates interaction among students in the classroom. The students will have ample opportunities to strengthen their subject specific knowledge vertically as well as horizontally. In the process of student collaboration with other students, they get to know about the basics of various topics and sub-topics. In the absence of collaborative learning, the students would lose the opportunity of being acquainted with subject specific aspects whose knowledge is gained through extensive study, sharing and spreading knowledge among

themselves. If the students are deprived of the tangible practice of collaborative learning, this deprivation remains yet another hurdle in their way of attaining application capabilities.

Ineffective Learning Strategies

Ineffective learning strategies are another bottleneck for students to acquire application ability in academic context. Students often embrace an ineffective technique of cramming a lot of information just before examinations. They read and reread the contents only for the sake of keeping the information in their passive memory temporarily in its rigid form. Consequently, they fail to acquire analytical and application skills as and when needed. This tendency of ineffective learning strategies adversely impacts the academic career aside from their prospective professional growth. The study of Stephen Chew and Cerbin reveals that “students often use ineffective strategies such as rereading, highlighting, underscoring and cramming” (Ineffective learning ...). They also opine that “self-testing is a relatively effective learning strategy” the students however “tend to underuse it or use it ineffectively” (ibid). Hence, this aspect of students’ learning practice was tried to be verified by collecting the opinions from students in this regard.

When asked during the second phase of data collection through Yes/No questionnaire, whether they prefer “memorize and answer” the questions rather than “understand and answer” the same, 47.7% of students said “Yes”. Nearly half of the students, according to this survey, embraced an entirely unproductive learning strategy. This phenomenon stands against that of the previously mentioned survey facts regarding their learning strategies. As discussed earlier, when asked whether they have their own learning strategies, 87.6% of students said “Yes”!. However, for a later question, 47.7% of students mentioned that they prefer to memorize the learning contents through the process of rote memorization. If the rote learning is one of their learning strategies, they are assumed to be inefficient in applying their knowledge in practical real life situations. Ahmed Y. Majdoubeh writes that the rote learning causes the occurrence of “cognitive loss” in students. He further mentions when the students choose to acquire the knowledge by rote learning, “the curiosity and love of learning [among students] die, and the learner becomes much like a parrot: regurgitating a limited set of information with no meaningful employment or transfer into real-life situations” (Ahmed 2021). The inability to use the acquired knowledge in real-life

situations indicates their inability to apply what they have learnt in the classrooms. This inability results from the practices like rote learning.

Rote memorization is necessary for students at memorizing mathematical tables and periodic tables at elementary school level. Whenever it is necessary for them, they recollect from their rote memorization and utilize the same in the studies. However, the students at undergraduate level need to understand the underlying meaning of concepts and interpretations and retain the same in memory. The information which is understood and memorized systematically can be made use of productively as and when needed in real-life situations. If the students try to cram their brains with concepts and other bits of information in isolation without necessary brainstorming, they cannot acquire critical thinking skills which are a prerequisite for them to acquire application skills in problem solving.

During the first phase of data collection, 170 students participated in it. When asked whether they choose to learn the contents by heart, 42.9% agreed that they learn the contents by heart, while 15.9% strongly agreed and 21.2% partly agreed. Altogether, 80% of students choose to learn the contents by heart and present the answers as and when required. This is a concerning issue which weakens students' cognitive and critical thinking abilities and apply the same.

When asked whether they learn the contents by heart, 42.9% of students agreed that they do, while 15.9% strongly agreed and 21.2% partly agreed. This is a conscious expression of the truth. The answer by the students to this question is crucial in this research. The response of over 80% of students that they learn the contents by heart reveals the central cause for their lack of possession of application skills. During the first phase of the survey, the students who were the participants

chose the ideal answers, as they think, to the questions in the questionnaire instead of answering by evaluating their learning practices. However, as they admitted that they choose to learn the contents by heart, it is clear that it is this academic characteristic that makes them deprived of attaining the application capability.

When asked whether they are able to select their learning strategies, 87.6% students said, Yes! However, a considerable proportion of students, i.e., 46.3% of students agreed that they leave the difficult topics without studying them intensely, while 53.7% of students mentioned that they do not leave any topic without understanding it. Leaving a difficult topic without learning and mastering it by the students reveals a gap in their learning strategies. So, the students are to be enlightened on various learning strategies. Also, it is understood that several students answered the questions with their possible ideal answers rather than what they were really practicing. Nevertheless, it is concerning to know that 46.3% of students skip the difficult topics without studying them intensely. This happens due to the lack of motivation and self-motivation. The poor self-motivation in turn remains a causation for the occurrence of application failure. So long as the students remain in their comfort zones, they cannot attain inclusive knowledge. The study of Neel Raman reveals that “learning gives [one] mental strength, which also strengthens [one’s] mind” (5 Painful ...2016). Hence, leaving some topics without studying by a large proportion of students is a regressive academic phenomenon and thereby it causes application impediment among students.

Several other significant facts were revealed by this survey. Though there appears positive signs, revealing the learning-friendly attitude of students, the students are yet to be habituated to active adoption of such learning habits. Though 86.7% of students said that they had their own learning strategies, they, in fact, thought that they had their own learning strategies. However, when further inquired (interviewed) on the phone (to qualitatively ascertain their answers),

● Yes
● No

whether they could specify their own learning strategies they have been using, they said that they had no specific knowledge regarding this issue. This phenomenon shows that the students also evince interest in creating their own learning strategies though

they have not really done so. Similarly, a large number of students also mentioned that they are able to guess the contextual meaning of unknown words. This is a good sign of productive learning. This paves a stronger basement for the students to acquire the application ability if this skill is productively made use of by teachers. Another important discovery of this survey is that the students are nowadays using the Google website for their reference needs. They are looking for the meanings of the unknown words by using Google website as their reference source. 91.9% of the students mentioned that they use Google for knowing the meanings of unknown words while reading. It is a favorable academic aspect which would, in future, support the student fraternity in the acquisition of application capabilities in the classrooms, labs and in their prospective workplaces.

Constraints of Selective Attention

The meticulous comprehension of learning contents is a pre-requisite for students to acquire application skills. However, selective attention of the students remains a barrier for comprehending the lessons imparted. If the students selectively listen to the contents of the topic explained by the teacher, they fail to get a comprehensive understanding of all the parts of the lesson. Every part of the lesson is important as every part is connected to every other part in the text explained. Selective attention is sometimes advantageous for one when in the outside of the classroom. The selective attention gives scope for the person to be attentive at only a few selective phenomena so that he/she could focus deeply on a few selective phenomena. However, when it comes to classroom chores, the students are to be attentive throughout the lecture.

The most common constraints of selective attention are the students' lack of interest in studies. They text some messages on social media while the lecture goes on. The website study of Taking Learning Seriously reveals that "80% of college students admit that they text [to others] during class" while 15% of students mentioned that they would "send 11 or more texts in a single class period" (constraints of selective...). However, what the specific constraints that are found in the Indian classroom is a valid question that needs to be answered.

When asked whether they are selectively attentive while listening to lectures, 51.2% of students frankly agreed while 12.4% strongly and 17.1% partly agreed. In the last analysis, about 80% of students admitted that they are selectively attentive rather than being fully attentive to the text delivered by the faculty. This happens in the absence of tangible learning practice. The tangible teaching process constitutes the utilization of physical teaching aids by the faculty. Because of this tangible teaching practice, the students can be attentive to the lesson contents from beginning to ending. This tangible teaching-learning practice helps the students attain better cognition of lesson contents. The better cognition in turn helps them acquire application skills.

With the advent of smart phones and the availability of the internet, the people, regardless of their age groups, are obsessed with social media. So, the students at undergraduate level too are not an exception to it. However, most of the students who participated in this survey said that they would not answer WhatsApp messages while in the classroom. While 31.1% students admitted that they would respond to WhatsApp messages while listening to lecture sessions in the classroom, a substantial portion of students, i.e., 68.9% mentioned that they would not respond to them. Though it is truly remarkable that the 68.9% of students do not chat while listening to the lectures, a considerable portion of students, i.e., 31.1% get distracted from listening to the lectures, hindering their cognitive processes. When the students' cognitive processes are hindered, they cannot understand the learning contents critically. The poor comprehension with several gaps would surely make an adverse impact upon their application abilities. The study of Sanjeev Datta reveals that "poor listening skills often demonstrate difficulties in maintaining attention and concentration, leading to reduced academic productivity and overall learning potential" (7 Most Adverse...). Dan Bobinski writes in a business context that the poor listening "leads to

assumptions and misunderstandings” (Bobinski 2016). Similarly, the students also resort to assumptions while filling up the gaps of their understanding of the lesson. Consequently, they fail to comprehend the overall essence of the lesson content. This selective attention, being addicted to social media is a hindrance for the students to attain applications skills.

Constraints of Mental Effort and Working Memory

The students’ limited working memory is a constraint in their learning and application. A student at school or college is regularly taught a series of courses in a day. The students are to understand and remember the contents taught by the teachers. In addition, they are expected to apply their knowledge as and when required. However, the demonstration of lessons by a number of teachers in a day compels the students to remember and retain a lot of information, while their working memories are limited. If the faculty disseminate “seductive details” besides the content related facts, the students are prone to get deviated from the main topic and thereby their brains cannot retain the previously absorbed information. The study of Blikstein & Wilensky reveals that “the most common problem” that the students face is the “too much information” that the lesson material consists of. According to their study, “One count has it that an average engineering lecture introduces a new equation every 2.5 minutes and a new variable every 45 seconds” (Blikstein and Wilensky, 2010, cited from Schwartz, Tsang and Blair’s *The ABC of How We Learn*, 2016, p. 124). The amalgamation of some interesting facts which are otherwise considered seductive details may arouse interest in the students in the classroom. However, the students lose interest in the main topic by turning their attention to these seductively interesting but irrelevant facts. Hence the faculty are to ensure that the students are not burdened with too much cognitive load. Because, too much cognitive load remains a bottleneck for the students to apply in practical situations what they learn in the classroom.

Relevance of Industrial Visits and Internships - Application Skills

The periodical Industrial visits by students at undergraduate level are fallen into the category of tangible learning practice. They help students understand the practical utility of scientific and technological laws and principles practically in industries. With a preconceived notion that the periodical industrial visits of students help them acquire the capability of application, a question on industrial visits was given in the questionnaire of the first phase survey. While the industrial visits help them understand the abstract concepts concretely, the physical internships help them

apply their conceptual knowledge practically in the industrial workplaces. So, a question in this regard also included in the questionnaire.

When asked how often have they so far been taken to industrial tours or field trips, 130 students said that they had never been taken to any trip, while 94 students mentioned that they had been taken to industrial or field trip only once. 27 students said that they had been taken to trips twice, while 7 students said it was thrice. Only one student said that four times he had been taken to trips, while the remaining 24 students did not answer the question.

In accordance with the graphical information furnished above, a huge proportion of students in the survey stated that they had never been taken to any industrial visits nor field trips. This is a concerning phenomenon as the absence of industrial visits and field trips imply that the students are engaged only in classroom lectures and traditional laboratory practices. This absence would adversely impact their knowledge application abilities. They lose an opportunity of applying in prospective real world workplaces what they learn theoretically at college. Anand Pancholi asserts that “while college and its syllabus prepare students with theoretical knowledge, Industry visits can expose them to real-world problems and give them an idea on how to resolve them”. (Anand 2021). Anand further mentions in his article that the “industry visits would help students develop skill sets which include “technical know-how, critical thinking and problem solving” (ibid). However, when these industrial visits are organized systematically, they will yield desired results, that is to say the students would acquire application abilities.

When further inquired whether they were supplied with the required questionnaires to be filled every day at the end of the day during their internship, 56.9% of students said “No”. Providing the students and interns with necessary questionnaires helps them quantify the knowledge and record the same in the questionnaire both subjectively and objectively at the end of every day during industrial visits and physical internships. When the industrial visits are organized with the necessary questionnaires to be filled by the participants, they can have an opportunity of quantifying their day’s experience and assessing their practical learning in the workplace. They will be able to visualize concretely the concepts and theories they have learnt in the classroom when they are provided with the opportunities to visit industries at regular intervals. Their systemic noting down of what they observe and learn viz., technical know-how, working methods, current trends in technology and human resources management etc., at the workplace (industry) helps them keep in their long memory securely the knowledge they acquired through their active learning and interaction with the personnel there. These questionnaires help the instructors to “evaluate [students’] skills growth in terms of initial and final assessment” (Maddalena della Volpe 2017). The questionnaires filled out by interns would help both the

● Yes
● No

students and the instructors in application-based teaching-learning process. So, either the regular industrial visits or the periodical physical internships would positively contribute to the imparting of application skills to students when they are systematically organized with the provision of day-wise

questionnaires to students.

Intra-Departmental Seminar Sessions and Application Skills

The weekly or bi-weekly intra-departmental seminars help the students acquire deeper understanding into their study material. Instead of receiving learning contents passively, they actively interact with the text they need to present at the seminars. In the process of preparing for the prospective seminar presentation, the students explore the presentation contents from various perspectives to be ready for answering questions of their peers and instructors during query

sessions. So, these weekly or bi-weekly seminars, if used as a method of instruction, can help the students apply their knowledge they have acquired in the classrooms. The students who are deprived of the making intra-departmental presentations will have to lose an opportunity to acquire application skills in their academic learning. The research findings of Atara Sivan et al reveal that the student seminars inspire them to actively involve in learning which in turn helps them acquire “independent learning skills and the ability to apply knowledge” (Atara 2010). Hence, the weekly student seminar sessions if regularly conducted would help them increase their self-esteem and this would in turn helps them acquire the application ability. However, when asked the students whether they have intra-departmental seminar sessions at college, 55.8% students said “No”. This gap in academics needs to be filled for creating a tangible teaching-learning environment at college where the students are to acquire application skills.

Significance of Arts & Cultural Club Sessions and Application Skills

The active participation of students in Art and Cultural club sessions will help them acquire creativity, methods of improvisation and learning strategies and so on. These skills will help them apply what they learn in the classroom. When asked whether they have an Arts and Cultural Club sessions, 80.2% of students said "No". Sigmund Freud opines [in the context of explaining Oedipus complex] that the artists have capabilities of deeper thinking, unravelling hidden causes behind even the most sensitive psychological issues. Active involvement by students in arts and cultural activities help them acquire the quality of creativity. Also, their active participation in Arts and Cultural club activities will help them establish their unique identity which in turn boosts their morale in the academic environment.

Next, their active participation in arts and cultural club activities will help them acquire imaginative capabilities and these capabilities in turn help them be innovative in their academics and prospective workplaces. The students who actively involve in arts and cultural club activities can deeply understand the texts by reading between lines and communicate verbally with others effectively. The research findings of National Center for Education Statistics further mentioned

● Yes
● No

that “the exposure [of students] to various activities [cultural activities] and opportunities to express themselves, build self-esteem, and develop social skills...”

(ibid). However, it was discovered through this survey that the exposure to creative literary works is almost not found in the academic lives of students. This phenomenon suggests that the students are entirely engaged in learning sciences and technology without even partial acquaintance with aesthetics. This would be a cause for their lacking application abilities.

Self-Esteem is one of the necessary qualities which help students acquire the skill of the practical application of what they have theoretically learnt in the classroom. Zining Liu's study also asserts the same that the "Arts education" positively influences their [students'] "cognitive development and academic performance" (Zining Liu 2023). These aspects of cognitive development and academic performance would help the students acquire the application skills. So, the conduct of Arts & Cultural Club sessions would positively impact the students' academics and application capabilities.

Relevance of Sports & Yoga Sessions

Aside from Arts and Cultural club sessions, the regular weekly Sports and Yoga sessions help the students enhance their cognitive ability and concentration power. This will in turn help them perform better in their academics and thereby their application skill set is bettered. The study of YSN Live reveals that "sports play a significant role in enhancing students' mental health and well-being, which is closely linked to academic performance" (Exploring the impact... 2024). Besides Sports, Yoga too helps the students "improve body-mind connection" (Important Benefits ... 22 May 2024). The active participation in sports allows the students to employ various theoretically learned techniques in different contexts creatively. Their active participation in sports & yoga sessions will function as implicit motivational factors and therefore the students will enthusiastically move ahead, attempting to apply a previously learned technique in a new situation. This will help them acquire and enhance their application skills. They master the patterns of applying what they have learnt theoretically.

However, when asked whether they have any weekly Sports and Yoga sessions, 72.4% of the students said “No”. This phenomenon implies the deprivation of students from the benefits which they can derive from weekly Sports and Yoga sessions. The research findings of Fernando Munoz Bullon et al asserts that the “participation in formal sporting activities is associated with higher grades among students at the university” where the research was carried out (Fernando 2017). The weekly sessions of Sports and Yoga have no explicit connection with students’

application capabilities. However, these sessions, if conducted systematically, would implicitly contribute to students’ knowledge application abilities. While the sports help them achieve good physical and mental fitness, Yoga helps them better their cognitive skills and longer span of concentration. These two

skills are a prerequisite for students to acquire application skills during academics and their prospective careers.

More Lecture Sessions & the Deficiency of Tangible Learning Practice

It is impracticable to use all the necessary tangible teaching-learning material during the traditional lecture sessions. Also, it is more difficult in the classrooms at technology institutes. So, this unfavorable aspect compels educators to schedule more lecture sessions than other tangible teaching-learning processes. However, more lecture sessions with a less number of practical sessions would not yield a desired result in regard to the attempts of improving the application skills of students. So, a correct mode of tangible teaching practice is more feasible during the practical sessions if the labs equipped with necessary tangible infrastructure. When asked whether they have more lecture sessions than the practical ones, 70.3% of students said, “Yes”. This indicates a phenomenon that the students have been deprived of tangible learning practices at their respective learning places. So long as the students are made to listen and receive knowledge theoretically in the traditional classroom, they cannot acquire critical thinking and problem solving abilities. The possession of these two skills by students is a prerequisite for them to achieve the ability of knowledge application in practical situations.

Next, the theoretical lecture sessions in the conventional lecture halls which are conducive only for receptive knowledge are not collaboration friendly for students. The labs will serve this purpose making students communicative and collaborative with one another while acquiring the practical knowledge of the lessons they have learnt in the classroom. While having the collaborative study with their peers in the laboratories, they develop creativity in regard to technical aspects, actively engaging in problem solving. Besides all the above skills, the students can also achieve firsthand knowledge and experience in using various tools, equipment and software tools in the labs. The students can have deeper understanding when they experiment, testing the theories in the labs. This will help them achieve academic autonomy. Hence, the academic schedule with more practical sessions will help the students acquire the application abilities. However, the survey finding that 70.3% of students have more lecture sessions than the lab sessions reveals that the students are subject to the deprivation of tangibly learning opportunities at their respective learning places. This is a phenomenon which causes the existence and persistence of application skill deficiency in students.

Nevertheless, 60.8% of students, when asked whether they wait till someone clears their doubts, said, “No”. They said, they would consult the available reference sources to clear their doubts instead of waiting for someone who can come and clear their doubts in academics. The above two findings reveal a hidden strength of students of this generation. Though the students do not have sufficient number of practical sessions, they have a potential innate ability of making a self-regulated study, trying to learn, clearing their doubts by using the available sources of learning. The experimental study of Patricia Fell reveals that the “hands-on laboratory work adds value to student learning in developing understanding and knowledge of the biosciences” (Patricia et al 2015). This positive aspect of students needs to be harnessed productively while imparting them necessary application skills.

Other Causes for Application Skills Deficiency

Next, when asked whether they [students] always give consent to their friend’s invitation to somewhere (movie/amusement parks etc.,) even if they have some academic work at that moment, 68.9% of students said, “No”. However, 31.1% of students said, “Yes”. This is obviously larger in number. The dereliction of 31 students out of every hundred in regard to their studies is concerning. One who has no goal cannot utilize one’s inherent capabilities optimally. The above 31 students

in every hundred are goalless and therefore they keep aside their books and go to the theatre when their friends propose. This is another factor which makes the students lack application capabilities.

When asked the students whether they have an English Language Lab with an adjoining Communication Skills Lab, 70.3% of students said, “Yes”. 29.7% of students said that they had no Lab. Though 70.3% of students had English Language Lab exposure, only 0.7% of students answered a question on reading comprehension in English. The question is as follows: Although she was fatigued, she managed to finish the race, but her brother, who was in better shape, fell behind in the last mile. How will the meaning of the sentence change if the comma after the word 'brother' is removed? Kindly try to answer this [in words]. When asked whether there would be any difference in the meaning of the sentence if the comma in the above sentence is deleted, except two students out of 283, nobody was able to give the correct explanation why there would be a change in the meaning of the sentence. This phenomenon remains the evidence why the students usually lack the application capabilities. Because, the pre-requisite for the possession of application capabilities is the flawless understanding of the learning contents. If they fail to understand the text [learning content], they inevitably fail to apply what they learn in the classroom.

When asked whether they would often visualize the hidden scientific or technological theories (Maths, Physics, Chemistry, Management Sciences, technology, AI, DS, Machine learning theories etc.) while participating in experiments in the labs as well as in their virtual internships, 63.2% of students said, “Yes”. However, a large proportion of the students, i.e., 36.8% of students said, “No”. This finding reveals that 37 students in every hundred are embracing the rote learning of scientific theories and technology. The students who do not evince interest in developing observation skills will fail to apply their knowledge in practical situations. The acquisition of knowledge through sincere learning classroom and keen observation in the labs is necessary for students to be able to rationally apply their acquired knowledge in practical situations. This becomes a possible reality only when the students are goal-oriented in regard to their academics and prospective job careers.

The responses of students for the following questions make one understand that the students think that they have set their respective goals whereas they have not known what a goal is all about. When asked whether they have any academic goal besides a prospective job goal, 73.9

% of the students said, “Yes”. However, when asked whether their mental life includes more other thoughts such as the unnecessary chatter, gossiping, daydreaming etc., than those related to their present studies viz., lessons, projects, referencing etc., 49.2% of the students admitted by saying, “Yes”. Those who do not have consistency and single-minded devotion in their efforts are not

● Yes
● No

expected to achieve their goals which are specific and time bound. 49.2% of students admitted that they give their mind to the activities other than their studies. 68.9% of students said, their academic works are more important than accepting

their friend’s invitation to a movie or an amusement park. 73.9% of students said that they have a goal. These two responses are in compliance with each other. However, when asked whether they are often preoccupied with thoughts other than their academic works, 42.9% students said, “Yes”. This means, they have an aspiration to achieve something good, but they do not know the difference between a goal and a mere aspiration. The participants in this survey failed to answer the question whether they can distinguish between a goal and the purpose of life. Based on this inquiry, it is understood that the students fail to add necessary action in regard to the fulfilment of their aspirations.

Major Findings

The discourse which has so far been done reveals a nexus between the lack of tangible learning practice and its consequent effects in regard to the students’ deficiency of application abilities.

The hypothetical statement, the lack of tangible learning practices in the classroom is the central cause for the lack of application skills in students, is hereby asserted with the following findings:

- The students initially expressed their self confidence that their skill set would improve. However, later, when they were probed deeply by asking whether they could reach the level of their role models, 64% of the students said, “No”. The lack of tangible learning practice remained a chief cause behind their lack of good self-esteem and self-confidence.

So, this phenomenon adversely impacts the students' endeavors of the acquisition of application skills.

- The researcher tried to know whether the students possess metacognitive skills by asking them whether they would have their own learning strategies. They mentioned that they had. However, they admitted, answering other questions, that they would skip difficult topics and learn the [remaining] course contents by heart. While the skipping of difficult topics would prevent them from meticulous understanding of the course, the learning of contents by heart could be regressive and this phenomenon would usually persist in the absence of the tangible learning practices. The acquisition of metacognition by students is possible only in the academic environment wherein the tangible learning practices are prevalent. The aspect of the lack of meta-cognitive skill is another important cause for the lack of application skills in students.
- 65% of the students frankly admitted that they would commit errors even after they were imparted correctly by the faculty. This happens due to the lack of tangible learning practice for students. It is due to the lack of tangible learning practice in the classroom, the students failed to have trust in the faculty's teaching inputs and thereby they committed errors in spite of correct teaching inputs by the faculty. The mistrust is another cause for the students' inability to apply their knowledge as this mistrust prevents them from correct understanding of the learning contents and applying the same as and when required.
- 80% of the students admitted that they would learn the contents through rote memorization rather than understanding the contents and keep them in active memory. As earlier stated, the rote memorization is regressive and unproductive. The students who embrace the rote memorization as one of their strategies can never apply the isolated pieces of the information they stored in their memories as and when required. This phenomenon of rote memorization of contents by students usually exists in the absence of the tangible teaching-learning practices. The students, without having an alternative productive learning environment at their respective learning places would embrace this unproductive rote memorization technique. This practice is an obstacle in the way of their attainment of application skills.
- Next, though the students stated that they were able to understand the new lesson contents without prior background knowledge, they processed even this question with the help of

all their previously acquired linguistic knowledge only. It is due to their inability in understanding the depth of the question, they opined so. The intention of the researcher in asking this question is to know whether they have the habit of reading other than the classroom notes. It was understood by the way they answered this question that they least bother about acquiring the prior background knowledge of their learning contents and courses by consulting reference material as part of their pursuit of their respective academic programs. Tangible learning not only includes activity-based learning, but also an active learning, making use of the available tangible learning resources. So, this attribute of students prevents them from critically understanding the lesson contents and causes their inability to apply what little they learn at their respective learning places.

- 80% of the students mentioned that they would be selectively attentive during their lecture sessions. This is an inevitable consequence of the teaching practice of delivering pure oral lectures without tangible teaching aids and simulations. This phenomenon casts a severe challenge to the students in their attempts to acquire application skills.
- While 46% of students mentioned that they had never been to industrial visits or engaged in field work, 33% said they went on an industrial visit once so far. This phenomenon would get them deprived of tangible learning opportunities. Because of this phenomenon, the students would lose the opportunities to physically see an abstract scientific law in the running machinery and equipment at industries. This phenomenon adversely impacts their cognitive and application abilities.
- More than half of the students mentioned that they had no intra-departmental seminar sessions. Discussions and debates are a part and parcel of tangible learning approach. Students could cognize complex concepts and theorems while they explain the same before their class-mates. There is also a possibility of sharing inputs mutually during these presentation sessions. This method of discussions was missing in the academic schedule of the students who took part in the surveys. This phenomenon in which the tangible learning practice is absent inevitably becomes a contributory cause for the failure of acquiring application skills by students.
- Over 70% of students mentioned that they had more lecture sessions rather than practical ones. This pattern of imparting course contents is against the approach of tangible teaching-learning approach. Pure lecture method is not apt for imparting abstract scientific concepts.

This causes the students' failure in applying what they learn at their respective learning places.

- Aside from the above aspects, the students had no Arts Club activities and Sports & Yoga sessions. These activities would implicitly help the students acquire creativity and self-organization skills, functioning as motivational force for them to grow intellectually. Their acquired creativity would make them creative in academic situations too. Most of the students, however, mentioned that they had no such sessions and so there is a greater possibility that this phenomenon would stand as an obstacle in their way of attaining application skills.
- The summarized form of findings mentioned above reveals a gap in the teaching-learning process which is to be filled up with tangible teaching-learning processes at every educational institute. All the findings mentioned above testify that the students lack application capabilities. The Indian education system in which pro-application skill methods were embedded ages ago is still struggling to produce, in large numbers, the educated youth with necessary application skills.
- To sum up, the ancient Gurkuls imparted education by employing both lecture and discussions as teaching methods and thereby made their pupils ready to lead social lives in compliance with the then socio-economic needs. So, the ancient Gurkuls attained their academic objective by making pupils employ their acquired knowledge and skills in their real life situations.

In the later medieval era, various courses such as languages, literature besides mathematics and astronomy were imparted to pupils at schools. It is rationally deduced that the medieval education system in India also catered to the needs of the-then production system by facilitating students to acquire knowledge in courses which are necessary to attain chores in their daily social lives.

The east India Company introduced English education. Later, the British colonial government implemented the same. The modern sciences and Mathematics was imparted to pupils in the modern age. This modern education system was upheld and implemented in the institutes established by the then freedom fighters. These institutes contributed to the sprout of new ideas and eventually resulted in the attainment of independence. So, these educational institutes also functioned effectively catering to the needs of the then production system. Even though there was

the dearth of tangible tools and devices at the-then educational institutes, the students proactively made use of the resources available and did well in their respective prospective workplaces with their educational standards. Especially, the western thought they learnt about in their classrooms made them apply their knowledge in the then ongoing freedom movement. So, the-then education system had been conducive to the-then socio-political requirements.

However, the teaching-learning processes at educational institutes in India have not been on par with the socio-economic, and political needs of contemporary society since Independence. Consequently, the students are often found with insufficient application skills. The same is ascertained by the analysis of the recently collected data inductively in this research that the students are lacking application skills due to the causes discussed above. Hence, the hypothesis that the lack of tangible learning practices in the classroom is the central cause for the lack of application skills in students is proved true through the above qualitative dominant quantitative research which was centered on the research question, “why do students, in general, often fail to apply their knowledge in their real life productive situations?” However, the causes for the absence of the aforementioned tangible teaching-learning processes needs to be explored and examined in the spheres of the country’s economy and politics aside from the world outlook of the top rung educators of the Indian educational institutes. This research problem is expected to be taken up by future researchers.

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